

with dilute solution and low current, and since we have demonstrated that many anomalous features accompany electrolysis under this condition (called non-Faradaic electrolysis¹⁻³), it is likely that the explanation in these two cases may have something in common. Since hydrated electron formation near the cathode has been one of the suggested explanations of non-Faradaic electrolysis we may assume that a steady state concentration of hydrated electrons builds up inside the cathode chamber, which leak out leading to the enhancement of current. This is theoretically possible because electrons are being pumped in at the rate of about 10^{15} electrons/sec at about 1 mA whereas the hydrated electrons get annihilated at a rate constant of the order of 10^9 - 10^{11} per sec. So the cathode chamber after some time becomes a veritable storehouse of electrons which leak out at a much faster rate than the migration speed of ions. So electronic conduction takes place along with ionic conduction and is responsible for the $+\Delta i$ -effect. This build-up of electrons near the cathode which is almost instantaneous is responsible for the observed reduction of dissolved nitrogen to ammonia in a similar apparatus as reported by Palit⁴.

Any way, it appears that some kind of extra 'pumping' action of charged carriers under the action of an electric field comes into play on interposition of a cellophane membrane particularly near the cathode.

Since a good portion of the $+\Delta i$ is instantaneous it is expected that A.C. would also show this $+\Delta i$ -effect. We have found this to be true with two kinds of experiments. Firstly, by using mains A.C. we have found that by simple immersion of a cellophane membrane between two electrodes, with water as the electrolyte, there is an upward 'kick' of the microammeter and on subsequent removal of the cellophane a downward 'kick'; and this could be repeated any number of times. Secondly, the measured conductivity of water with a conventional A.C. bridge increases by nearly a factor of two when a cellophane membrane is dipped inside the conductivity cell between the two electrodes; furthermore this change is found to be reversible. It is evident that the current conduction mechanism through water or a poorly conducting solution changes considerably in the presence of a cellophane membrane in a way which is rather difficult to understand.

References

1. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 636.
2. S. R. PALIT, *Chemistry (Amer. Chem. Soc.)*, 1975, 48(4), 16.
3. C. K. GOSNELL and M. VENUGOPALAN, *Chemistry (Amer. Chem. Soc.)*, 1976, 49(4), 27.
4. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 328.

Some Observations on the Electronic Spectra of Terpyridyl Copper Chloride.

K. BANERJEE and S. K. BOSE

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-9, India

Manuscript received 7 December 1976, accepted 21 March 1977

THE commonest structure of the pentacoordinated complexes of metals is a trigonal bipyramid (D_{3h}) although a few square pyramidal structures are known. The most well-known example of a trigonal bipyramidal complex of copper is monoterpyridyl copper chloride. Although the earlier¹ x-ray data suggested that zinc terpyridyl complex is a distorted trigonal bipyramid, with which the copper complex is isomorphous, the latter work² indicates the structure to be square pyramid. Each unit cell contains two complex molecules, the chlorine atom of the second molecule coordinates (called hydrogen bonded) with the copper atom of the first giving an effectively bridged structure. In the latter case we have effectively hexacoordinated complexes with three N and three Cl atoms surrounding the copper atom commonest symmetry of such a structure will be D_3 . X-ray study by Goldschmid and Stephenson³ shows Zn (terpy) Cl_2 to have 62% trigonal bipyramidal character. Einstein and Penfold⁴ have shown Zn (terpy) Cl_2 has five coordinated trigonal bipyramidal structure.

An ideal trigonal bipyramidal structure has the symmetry D_{3h} and from the d orbital energy level scheme⁵ for a d^9 atom such as copper (a system with one hole) two transitions are expected, viz ${}^2E' \leftarrow {}^2A_1'$ and ${}^2E'' \leftarrow {}^2A_1'$, the latter is electronically forbidden. If instead we regard the complex to be trigonal (D_3), then we expect the following transitions ${}^1A_1 \leftarrow {}^2E$ (xy polarised) and ${}^2E \leftarrow {}^2E$. The latter will split into two transitions of species A and E one being Z and the other xy polarised.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of powdered crystals of [Zn (Terpy)] Cl_2 (—) and powdered crystals of [Zn (terpy)] Cl_2 , [Cu(terpy)] Cl_2 (-----)

Good single crystal of Cu (terpy) Cl₂ itself could not be grown. So the absorption spectra of polycrystalline Cu (terpy) Cl₂ in the host lattice of Zn (terpy) Cl₂ were recorded in a set up described by Chakraborty and Basu⁶. Spectra of powdered Zn (terpy) Cl₂ (Fig. 1) show band at 22650 cm⁻¹ and 18000 cm⁻¹. Single crystal of Cu (terpy) Cl₂ in the host lattice of Zn (terpy) Cl₂ were then powdered and its recorded spectra show a new band at 14800 cm⁻¹. This new band is due to the copper complex and is in close agreement with the solution spectral data⁷ which shows one absorption band at 680 m μ (14440 cm⁻¹) with E_M = 80.

The crystal spectra of a single crystal of the copper complex in the host lattice of the zinc complex with light polarised along the long and short axis of the crystal (Fig. 2), show two bands at 14500 cm⁻¹ and 14110 cm⁻¹ appearing in both states of polarization while a weak band at 16600 cm⁻¹ occurs only in one state of polarization.

Fig. 2 Absorption spectra of a single crystal of [Zn(terpy)]Cl₂, [Cu(terpy)]Cl₂ in polarised light.

The spectral data, therefore, are in conformity with a distorted trigonal bipyramidal structure for Cu (terpy) Cl₂.

Acknowledgement

We thank Prof. S. Basu for discussions during the course of the work.

References

1. D. E. C. CORBRIDGE and E. G. COX, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 594.
2. M. GARLOCH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1966, 1317.
3. E. GOLDSCHMID and N. C. STEPHENSON, *Acta Cryst.*, 1970, B26, 1867.
4. F. W. B. EINSTEIN and B. R. PENFOLD, *Acta Cryst.*, 1966, 20, 924.
5. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, A study of metal complexes in solution, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Lond. Second printing 1958, 69.
6. A. CHAKRABORTY and S. BASU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, 17, 55.
7. R. HOGG and R. G. WILKINS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 341.

Determination of Carboxylic Acids Via Formation of Benzylthiuronates.

J. V. KRISHNA REDDY and K. S. BOPARAI

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain, 456 010

Manuscript received 7 June 1976, revised 4 February 1977, accepted 18 March 1977

CHARACTERIZATION of carboxylic acids as benzylthiuronates¹ is valuable, however, the melting points of many of these salts lie within a narrow range of temperature and the values also depend on the experimental technique employed for the determination. Therefore, it is often desirable that the identification may be confirmed by some independent method. Titrimetric determination of benzylthiuronates with perchloric acid² in anhydrous acetic acid medium using crystal violet indicator affords a useful method for the determination of equivalent weights of the corresponding acids. The water of crystallization present in certain salts can interfere with the determinations. Further, the method suffers from the usual shortcomings of non-aqueous titrimetry. Benzylisothioureia, which is liberated when benzylthiuronates are treated with alkali, undergoes spontaneous decomposition to benzylmercaptan which can be estimated titrimetrically with sodium *o*-hydroxymercuri benzoate³ using thiofluorescein indicator; the procedure, however, has been tested with a few carboxylic acids only. The decomposition of benzylisothioureia to benzyl mercaptan has been found to be quantitative and the iodimetric determination of the latter is an accurate procedure for the determination of equivalent weights of carboxylic acids. The method was tested on benzylthiuronium chloride and benzylthiuronates of carboxylic and sulphonic acids. Unlike the Berger's procedure, the present method is applicable to sulphonic acids as well. The accuracy of the procedure is comparable to that of Berger's. Further, the procedure is convenient as it is devoid of the shortcomings of the non-aqueous procedure. The procedure is particularly valuable in the case of an acid which is not available in the pure form and direct titrimetric determination with a base is not sufficiently accurate. As such, the procedure merits recommendation. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

Determination of Benzylthiuronates.

Benzylthiuronates are prepared according to the reported procedure¹. The salt (75 to 200 mg) is weighed into an iodine flask and dissolved in 20% ethanol. Sodium hydroxide (10 ml, 10% W/V) is introduced and the contents of the flask are swirled for a few minutes. Hydrochloric acid (10 ml, 3N) is then added to acidify the solution. A little more ethanol is added if the solution becomes cloudy. The solution is titrated against 0.05 N iodine using starch indicator.